

ENHANCING THE MECHANICAL AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF RECYCLED EVOH FILMS WITH NANO- SILICA INCORPORATION

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the reinforcement of poly(ethylene-co-vinyl alcohol) (EVOH) films—recycled through the STRAP (Solvent-Targeted Recovery and Precipitation) process with SiO₂ nanoparticles at varying concentrations (0.1, 0.25, and 0.5 wt.%). EVOH was selectively dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and SiO₂ NPs was dispersed before precipitation of the pellets. The recovered EVOH composites were extruded into blown films and characterized for mechanical, thermal, and structural properties. FTIR analysis confirmed the incorporation of SiO₂ through Si–O–Si bonding, while SEM imaging revealed dispersion quality at different loadings. Thermal (TGA, DSC) and mechanical (tensile) tests demonstrated that the 0.1 wt.% SiO₂ sample offered the most significant improvements, with an elastic modulus of 0.25 GPa and a maximum tensile stress of 11.71 MPa. Higher loadings (0.25 and 0.5 wt.%) resulted in decreased performance, likely due to nanoparticle agglomeration disrupting polymer continuity. DSC results showed that the 0.1 wt.% addition increased melting and crystallization temperatures, indicating enhanced thermal resistance, while higher loadings had the opposite effect. XRD analysis further supported these findings. A broad peak at $2\theta \approx 23^\circ$ confirmed the amorphous nature of SiO₂ grafted to the recycled EVOH matrix. Relative crystallinity increased with 0.1 wt.% SiO₂ but declined at higher concentrations due to poor dispersion and aggregation. Therefore, low concentrations of nano-SiO₂ significantly enhanced the mechanical strength, thermal stability, and crystallinity of recycled EVOH films. These findings demonstrate the potential of nanoparticle-assisted upcycling to improve the performance of barrier polymers recovered from multilayer packaging waste.

1 INTRODUCTION

The growing accumulation of packaging waste has led to widespread interest in recycling strategies. However, materials recovered through these processes often suffer from inadequate thermal and mechanical performance, which restricts their reuse in demanding applications. One promising solution is the incorporation of nanoscale additives, which can significantly improve the functional properties of recycled polymers. Nanoparticles are particularly effective due to their high surface area, which facilitates stronger interactions at the interface between polymer chains and filler particles. These interactions can enhance properties such as strength, thermal resistance, and durability in polymer nanocomposites [1]. Silicon dioxide (SiO₂) is a frequently applied inorganic nanoparticle known for its three-dimensional framework of SiO₄ units. It exists both in naturally occurring crystalline structures—like quartz and in synthetic, non-crystalline (amorphous) forms [2]. Owing to its strong chemical resistance, heat tolerance, and mechanical strength, SiO₂ serves as a valuable additive in polymer matrices, helping to enhance durability and barrier efficiency in composite materials such as films and coatings [1,2]. In particular, amorphous SiO₂ has been recognized as a biocompatible material, making it suitable for use in food-grade and pharmaceutical applications without known adverse health effects [3]. This research focuses on the use of nano-SiO₂ as an additive in recycled ethylene vinyl alcohol (EVOH) films obtained through a selective dissolution process. The study examines the influence of different SiO₂ loadings (0.1, 0.25, and 0.5 w/w%) on the films' chemical, mechanical, and thermal properties, aiming to enhance the performance of recycled EVOH for practical reuse.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

EVOH pellets containing 48 mol% ethylene (grade G176B) were supplied by Kuraray Co., Ltd., Houston, TX. Amorphous silicon dioxide (SiO₂) nanoparticles and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), 99.5%, were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO), with DMSO serving as the solvent for dissolving the EVOH. Structural properties of the samples were analyzed from the X-ray Diffraction (XRD) pattern. The XRD pattern of all the samples were recorded using Rigaku Smartlab with a Cu K α source ($\lambda=1.5406$ Å) in the 2θ range of 10–80°, scanning rate of 1°/min and step size of 0.01. A Labtech Ultra Micro Film Blowing Line (model LUMF- 150) single-screw extrusion extruder was utilized to produce films. The films' mechanical properties were examined through tensile tests conducted with a Zwick Roell Z2.5 universal testing machine. The testing followed the ASTM D882- 10 standard, using a 20 N ceramic load cell, and five samples from each batch were tested to ensure consistent results. The Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of the polymer films were obtained using a Shimadzu IRTracer- 100 spectro photometer in transmittance mode over wavelengths ranging from 500 to 4000 cm⁻¹ at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out in a TA Q 500TGA. PSPW (15 mg) samples were heated from 30°C to 600°C at a heating rate of 10°C/min under a nitrogen atmosphere.

The recycling process began by dissolving EVOH films in DMSO at a 1:10 weight-to-volume ratio. Silica nanoparticles were then added to the solution and dispersed using 10 minutes of sonication to ensure uniform distribution. Precipitation was carried out using distilled water as an antisolvent, after which the recovered EVOH pellets were thoroughly washed three times with distilled water to remove residual DMSO. The resulting material was extruded into films with a thickness of 0.03 mm and subjected to mechanical and thermal characterization. Techniques such as Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) confirmed the effective incorporation of SiO₂ NPs into the EVOH matrix.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FTIR spectra (Fig. 1a) of neat EVOH and EVOH films incorporated with varying concentrations of SiO₂ nanoparticles (0.1, 0.25, and 0.5 w/w%), compared with pure SiO₂ nanoparticles. The characteristic Si–O–Si stretching vibration around 1100 cm⁻¹ confirms the successful incorporation of silica into the polymer matrix. Progressive shifts and intensity changes in the spectra indicate increasing interaction between EVOH and SiO₂ with higher nanoparticle loading.

Thermal analysis (Fig. 1b-d) revealed that the incorporation of nano-SiO₂ significantly improved the thermal stability of recycled EVOH films, particularly at low concentrations. The addition of 0.1 w/w% nano-SiO₂ increased the melting and crystallization temperature, indicating enhanced thermal resistance and molecular ordering. In contrast, a higher concentration of 0.5 w/w% led to a decrease in both transition temperatures, likely due to nanoparticle agglomeration that disrupted the polymer's crystalline structure. These trends are consistent with prior findings on SiO₂ based nanocomposites [7]. Therefore, the addition of SiO₂ NPs, particularly at low concentrations, effectively enhanced the mechanical and thermal properties of recycled EVOH films. These results highlight the potential of SiO₂ NPs to improve the performance of recycled polymeric materials, offering a sustainable approach to high performance film production. The mechanical performance of EVOH/SiO₂ nanocomposites (Fig. 1c) varied significantly with SiO₂ content. The 0.1 w/w% SiO₂ sample exhibited the best reinforcement, showing a 177.78% increase in elastic modulus and an 88.87% improvement in F_{max}, indicating excellent nanoparticle dispersion and strong interaction with the polymer matrix. At 0.25%, both modulus and F_{max} dropped sharply to 33.33% and 34.83% improvement, respectively, likely due to poor dispersion and disruption of polymer continuity. With 0.5% SiO₂, a partial recovery was observed possibly due to the rigid filler effect, although dispersion remained suboptimal. Therefore, the 0.1% concentration demonstrated the most favorable mechanical enhancement. The reduction in mechanical properties at higher concentrations might be attributed to the inadequate formation of intermolecular hydrogen bonds, as reported by Voon et al. (2012), and nanoparticle aggregation, which disrupts the uniform distribution of nanoparticles within the polymer matrix [4-6].

Figure 1: Impact of nano SiO₂ on EVOH polymer properties: **a)** FTIR spectra **b)** TGA analysis, **c)** DSC crystallization analysis, **d)** DSC melting analysis, and **e)** Tensile test analysis.

The crystalline structure of SiO₂ nanoparticles and the changes in the crystalline structures of EVOH after incorporating SiO₂ NPs and their relative crystallinity (%) were obtained using XRD [8]. Due to the addition of the nanoparticles inside the polymer structure, some alterations of the matrix and molecular packaging crystalline structure can be found. For packaging, nanomaterials added inside this structure affect crystallinity, barrier properties, mechanical performance, and among others [9,10]. The XRD pattern of SiO₂ nanoparticles (Fig. 2a) displays a broad, prominent peak characteristic of

amorphous silica, consistent with the findings of Sun et al. (2017), who observed a similar peak around $2\theta = 23^\circ$, confirming the amorphous nature of SiO₂ NPs used in alite–calcium sulfoaluminate (CSA) cement-based nanocomposites [11].

Figure 2: Diffractograms of the **a)** SiO₂ and **b)** EVOH films and their nanocomposite films, varying SiO₂ percentage (0.1, 0.25, and 0.5%).

In Fig. 2b, a distinct diffraction peak appears at approximately $2\theta = 20\text{--}21^\circ$ in both neat EVOH and nanocomposite films containing SiO₂ NPs, corresponding to the semi-crystalline structure of EVOH. Notably, the addition of SiO₂ nanoparticles did not introduce new peaks or cause significant peak shifts, suggesting that the crystalline structure of EVOH remains largely unchanged. The relative crystallinity, 2θ values, peak area, and full width at half maximum (FWHM) obtained through peak deconvolution are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Relative Crystallinity (%) obtained from XRD diffractograms for SiO₂/EVOH composite films (0.1, 0.25, and 0.5 wt/wt%), area under the peak, and Full width at half maximum (FWHM) obtained by deconvolution of diffractograms.

Samples	Relative Crystallinity (%)	2θ degree	The area under the peak	Full width at half maximum (FWHM)
SiO ₂	15.91	----	----	----
Neat	5.98	20.60	0.50	1.36
0.1 w/w% SiO ₂	14.81	20.54	0.94	1.40
0.25 w/w% SiO ₂	7.49	20.43	0.70	1.96
0.5 w/w % SiO ₂	10.95	20.47	1.20	2.10

From the values presented in Table 1, relative crystallinity (%) increased when added 0.1 %. Increasing the percentage of SiO₂ nanoparticles for 0.25 and 0.5 w/w.%, a reduction of relative crystallinity was found. Wang et al. (2018) reported that there was an increase in the crystallinity of the PHBV-containing rice husk SiO₂ nanoparticles. However, exceeding 3 wt.% of nanoparticles, a reduction of the crystallinity was verified. Firstly, the increase can be associated with the anisotropic nucleation of the SiO₂ NPs. However, from its limit, this value can decrease due to the agglomeration of these nanoparticles into the polymer matrix [12]. Besides, the interaction between hydroxyl groups of the EVOH and SiO₂ nanoparticles could have created hydrogen bonds, thus forming a large amount of EVOH crystals around the SiO₂ nanostructures [13,14]. the nucleating action of the SiO₂ nanoparticles for 0.1 w/w.% inside the EVOH polymer matrix can create a tortuous pathway for the gases, increasing the barrier property of the food packaging [15].

4 CONCLUSIONS

Based on the comprehensive analysis of FTIR, tensile, thermal, and XRD data, it can be concluded that incorporating low concentrations of nano-SiO₂, particularly at 0.1 w/w%, significantly enhances the performance of recycled EVOH films. FTIR confirmed the successful interaction between SiO₂ and the EVOH matrix through Si–O–Si vibrational bands, with increasing interaction at higher loadings. However, the mechanical and thermal evaluations revealed that 0.1 w/w% SiO₂ yielded the highest improvements in modulus, F_{max}, and thermal transitions, attributed to uniform dispersion and strong interfacial bonding. XRD results further supported this by showing increased relative crystallinity at 0.1 w/w%, likely due to the nucleating effect of well-dispersed nanoparticles. Higher concentrations (0.25–0.5 w/w%) led to nanoparticle agglomeration, decreased crystallinity, and diminished mechanical and thermal benefits. Overall, the 0.1 w/w% SiO₂ NPs concentration presents an optimal balance of improved mechanical strength, thermal stability, and crystallinity without compromising structural integrity, offering a sustainable solution for upcycling EVOH-based packaging waste.

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